

1 Crevasse density, orientation, and temporal variability at 2 Narsap Sermia, Greenland

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5 ABSTRACT.

6 Mass loss from iceberg calving at marine terminating glaciers is one of
7 the largest and most poorly constrained contributors to sea level rise. How-
8 ever, our understanding of the processes controlling ice fracturing and crevasse
9 evolution is incomplete. Here, we use Gabor filter banks to automatically
10 map crevasse density and orientation through time on a ~ 150 km² termi-
11 nus region of Narsap Sermia, an outlet glacier of the southwest Greenland
12 Ice Sheet. We find that Narsap Sermia is dominated by transverse (flow-
13 perpendicular) crevasses near the ice front and longitudinal (flow-aligned)
14 crevasses across its central region. Crevasse orientation varies on sub-annual
15 timescales by more than 45° in response to seasonal velocity changes, and
16 also on multi-annual timescales in response to broader dynamic changes and
17 glacier retreat. Our results show a gradual up-glacier propagation of the zone
18 of flow-transverse crevassing coincident with frontal retreat and acceleration
19 occurring in 2020/21, in addition to sub-annual crevasse changes primarily
20 in transition zones between longitudinal to transverse crevasse orientation.
21 This provides new insight into the dynamics of crevassing at large marine-
22 terminating glaciers, and a potential approach for the rapid identification of
23 glacier dynamic change from individual satellite images.

24 INTRODUCTION

25 The future response of the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets to changing climatic conditions remains one
26 of the most uncertain factors in forecasts of future sea level rise (Pörtner and others, 2019; Masson-Delmotte
27 and others, 2021). The majority of the mass loss of these ice sheets occurs at marine-terminating glaciers,
28 which lose mass by calving icebergs directly into the ocean (Benn and others, 2007; Vieli and Nick, 2011).
29 Changes in the frontal conditions of marine-terminating glaciers can drive rapid glacier retreat (Nick and
30 others, 2009; Venteris, 1999; Kochtitzky and Copland, 2022), and can promote rapid ice thinning far from
31 the ice front due to dynamic glacier changes (e.g. Pritchard and others, 2009). The Greenland Ice Sheet
32 itself lost glacier area at a rate of $241.47 \pm 1.19 \text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$ (2000-2020; Kochtitzky and Copland, 2022),
33 and lost mass at a rate of $222 \pm 30 \text{ Gt/yr}$ (2013-2018; Shepherd and others, 2020). While there is a
34 well documented relationship between oceanic and atmospheric warming and marine-terminating glacier
35 retreat (Cowton and others, 2018; Fahrner and others, 2021), many of the controls on the rate of marine-
36 terminating glacier retreat remain poorly understood, limiting our understanding of present-day glacier
37 dynamics and our ability to forecast future glacier mass loss.

38 Understanding the retreat rates of marine terminating glaciers relies on identifying the glacier dynamic
39 conditions. Glacier dynamic conditions and changes are currently assessed primarily based on ice velocity
40 calculated using feature tracking, which relies the existence on coherent satellite image pairs with a suitably
41 low temporal baseline. In the case of fast flowing glaciers, conditions in fast flowing regions and close to the
42 calving front often cannot be resolved due to decorrelation or calving ice losses between the two images.
43 The region immediately up-glacier of the ice front is critical for our understanding of calving processes, so
44 we develop a method for the identification of glacier dynamic change from a single image.

45 Mass loss at marine-terminating glaciers occurs partly through iceberg calving, as fractures propagate
46 through the entire thickness of the glacier. Glacier flow delivers a constant flux of new ice to the glacier
47 front. A glacier's terminus position is stable if the rate of iceberg calving is approximately equal to the
48 flux of ice to the front, and retreating if the rate of calving exceeds the ice flux. Iceberg calving can drive
49 rapid glacier retreat (10^2 - 10^3 m/yr), particularly where glaciers terminate in deep water (Venteris, 1999;
50 Rivera and others, 2012; Moffat and others, 2018; Bondzio and others, 2018). In order for an iceberg to
51 calve, a fracture must penetrate through the entire ice thickness and separate one piece of ice from the rest
52 of the glacier. These fractures are known as crevasses, and are widely present in glacial environments.

Fig. 1. Diagram describing the main categories of crevasses, and their formation mechanisms.

53 Crevasses form due to tensile or shear stresses in the ice which locally exceed its strength. Crevasses
 54 are present on glaciers across a wide range of scales, from metre scale fractures in valley and cirque glaciers
 55 to rifts tens of kilometres long at the margins of the Antarctic Ice Sheet. Crevasses are thought to form
 56 approximately perpendicular to the principal stress direction: transverse or flow-perpendicular crevasses
 57 (oriented around 90° from the direction of ice flow) are commonly found in zones of longitudinal extension,
 58 while longitudinal or splaying crevasses (oriented approximately parallel to the direction of ice flow) are
 59 commonly found in zones of longitudinal compression (Figure 2). Lateral shear at the margins of a glacier
 60 often results in crevasses oriented around 45° from the valley walls (Nye, 1952; Glen and Perutz, 1955;
 61 Nye, 1955; Colgan and others, 2016; Hudleston, 2015; Jennings and Hambrey, 2021). Creep closure usually
 62 limits crevasse depth to a few tens of metres, and understanding the conditions under which crevasses may
 63 propagate through the entire ice column is key to evaluating the drivers of iceberg calving (Nye and Mott,
 64 1953; Nye and Perutz, 1957; Benn and others, 2007; Mottram and Benn, 2009).

65 A number of analytical and numerical approaches have been used to evaluate the influence of crevassing
66 on glacier calving, from simple ‘zero dimensional’ calving laws to full 3-D glacier models (e.g. Nye and
67 Perutz, 1957; van der Veen, 1998; Pralong and Funk, 2005; Mottram and Benn, 2009; Krug and others,
68 2014; Todd and others, 2018; Choi and others, 2018; Bassis and others, 2021; Crawford and others, 2021;
69 Cook and others, 2022). Certain early studies of calving bypass crevasses entirely, and relate glacier calving
70 rate to water depth at the ice front (Brown and others, 1982; van der Veen, 1998) or ice front height (Pfeffer
71 and others, 1997). These empirical models allow models to reproduce observed rates of ice retreat in some
72 cases, but are not physically based. More recent studies have proposed different calving models related to
73 ice dynamics and physical variables, for instance height-above-buoyancy models (Vielé and others, 2001),
74 crevasse depth criteria (Benn and others, 2007), von Mises tensile stress criteria (Morlighem and others,
75 2016; Choi and others, 2018), kinematic calving laws (Levermann and others, 2012), and linear elastic
76 fracture mechanics approaches (Yu and others, 2017). Advances in computational power have also enabled
77 the use of discrete element models to simulate crevasse calving, which can reproduce individual calving
78 events in greater detail (Benn and others, 2017; Gong and others, 2018; Cook and others, 2018; van Dongen
79 and others, 2020). Many advances in the numerical description of crevasses have been made over the past 20
80 years, but limitations remain in our understanding and numerical representation of crevasse penetration at
81 the ice front, and ice sheet models lack a universally applicable and computationally efficient representation
82 of calving. Large scale observations of crevasse evolution are therefore key to developing and evaluating
83 new crevasse models.

84 Crevasses form visible traces on the surface of glaciers, and can therefore be identified and monitored
85 remotely via ground, air, or satellite-based imagery. Manual identification of crevasses in remotely sensed
86 imagery dates back almost 50-years (e.g. Krimmel and Meier, 1975), and has been reviewed by Colgan
87 and others (2016) and Jennings and Hambrey (2021). The study of glacier surface crevasse patterns is
88 an key method in structural glaciology, and can yield insight into glacier strain history, current dynamics,
89 and future stability. Structural glaciology is a sub-discipline which aims to evaluate glacier processes using
90 their structural characteristics: crevasses, faults, folds, foliation, and more (Hudleston, 2015; Jennings and
91 Hambrey, 2021). For instance, crevasses were manually mapped at Worthington Glacier, USA (Harper and
92 others, 1998), Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Switzerland (Goodsell and others, 2005), Kvíárjökull, Svínafellsjökull,
93 and Fjallsjökull, Iceland (Phillips and others, 2017; Swift and others, 2018; Dell and others, 2019, ; respec-
94 tively), Isunguata Sermia, Greenland (Jones and others, 2018), and Fountain Glacier, Canada (Jennings

95 and others, 2022).

96 Semi-automated crevasse mapping methods are also used, including the use of histogram equalization
97 or edge enhancement image processing to facilitate manual crevasse identification (Colgan and others, 2011,
98 2016). However, manual or semi-automated crevasse identification is both subjective and time consuming,
99 preventing multi-temporal mapping of crevasses over large spatial areas. Therefore, a range of fully-
100 automated crevasse mapping techniques have also been developed: Bhardwaj and others (2016) used a
101 simple Landsat band ratio technique to map small crevasses on Shaune Garang glacier (Himalaya), Gong
102 and others (2018) used the Radon transform to evaluate linear features on a surging outlet of Austfonna
103 (Svalbard), Chudley and others (2021) compared a Random Forest classification to crevasse maps from
104 high-resolution elevation data, Lai and others (2020) used a neural network to identify Antarctica-wide
105 rifts using Mosaic of Antarctica imagery, and Zhao and others (2022) applied deep learning to Sentinel-
106 1 radar imagery to map fractures in Antarctic ice shelves. Despite the recent advances in automated
107 crevasse mapping, most existing techniques either require an extensive training dataset (e.g. machine
108 learning-based methods; Lai and others, 2020; Chudley and others, 2021; Zhao and others, 2022), or
109 only provide overview statistics instead of the location and attributes of individual crevasses (e.g. Radon
110 transform-based methods; Gong and others, 2018).

111 Here, we describe a new automated crevasse mapping method based on processing images with linear
112 feature detection kernels: Gabor filters. This method is computationally fast, does not require any training
113 data, and provides a map of individual crevasse locations. We apply this method to automatically map the
114 occurrence of crevasses on 6 years of Sentinel-2 data (224 images) on a ~ 150 km² region of Narsap Sermia,
115 an outlet glacier of the Greenland Ice Sheet. We also calculate glacier velocity maps so as to compare
116 crevasse fields to glacier velocity magnitude and direction. We use this data to explore the following three
117 research questions:

- 118 1. What is the spatial pattern and orientation of crevasses across a large marine-terminating glacier?
- 119 2. Is the distribution, extent, and orientation of crevasses constant through time, or does it exhibit seasonal
120 and/or multiannual changes?
- 121 3. What is the relationship between crevasse characteristics and glacier velocity?

Fig. 2. Location of Narsap Sermia in Greenland and within Nuup Kangerlua, and view of the glacier on from Sentinel-2.

122 STUDY AREA

123 Narsap Sermia is a large outlet glacier draining the south-west margin of the Greenland Ice Sheet, and
124 the closest marine-terminating glacier to Greenland’s capital and most populous city, Nuuk (Pearce and
125 others, 2018). Alongside Kangiata Nunaata Sermia and Akullerssuup Sermia, Narsap Sermia calves icebergs
126 directly into Nuup Kangerlua (Nuuk Fjord), which can be advected down-fjord and impede shipping routes
127 to Nuuk. The front of Narsap Sermia was stable close to its Little Ice Age position until the early 21st
128 century (Motyka and others, 2017), whereupon it has exhibited several episodes of rapid ice retreat (Motyka
129 and others, 2017; Davison and others, 2020), the latest of which is ongoing today. Narsap Sermia currently
130 terminates in moderate to shallow depth water (around 200 m; Morlighem and others, 2014), but a deep
131 subglacial trough is present around 5-20 km up-glacier from the 2022 calving front (Morlighem and others,
132 2014; Motyka and others, 2017). If Narsap Sermia’s calving front were to reach the retrograde slope at
133 the down-glacier edge of this subglacial trough, it could enter a phase of runaway retreat observed at other
134 marine-terminating glaciers (Venteris, 1999; Motyka and others, 2017). This runaway retreat might also be
135 associated with changes in calving style, affecting the quantity and size distribution of icebergs advected
136 towards Nuuk. Narsap Sermia has three subsidiary ice fronts terminating in ice-marginal lakes, including
137 the $\sim 20 \text{ km}^2$ glacial lake Iluliartôq. All three lakes have varying volumes and drain under the glacier,
138 with the lowermost lake remaining fully drained since the latest episode of frontal retreat (post 2014). The
139 societal importance of calving processes at Narsap Sermia, along with its high degree of crevassing and
140 ongoing frontal retreat, make it an ideal case study for spatio-temporal changes in crevassing.

141 METHODS

142 We implement a method to automatically detect and calculate the orientation of crevasses within satellite
143 images using a Gabor filter bank. A Gabor filter is composed of a sinusoidally modulated Gaussian kernel,
144 and is sensitive to image texture. By combining a bank of filters of different orientations, we extract
145 individual crevasse locations and orientations from optical satellite images (Figure 3). We describe the
146 attributes of the Gabor filter bank and crevasse detection in more detail in section S1 of the supplement.
147 This method is computationally rapid, extracts individual crevasse orientations, and does not require a
148 training dataset. We apply this method, which we term the Gabor crevasse detector (GCD), to all 10 m
149 resolution near-infrared (band 8) Sentinel-2 images of Narsap Sermia from the satellite launch in 2015 to

150 April 2022. We exclude all images in which the glacier is obscured by cloud cover or shadows, retaining
151 the 224 images in which the entire glacier area is unobstructed. As well as calculating a binary crevasse
152 mask and crevasse orientation map for each image, we calculate three crevasse statistics in 20 by 20 pixel
153 sub-regions. The three statistics are crevasse spatial density (the ratio of pixels classified as crevasses to
154 the total number of pixels in the sub-region), the median crevasse orientation, and the mean absolute
155 deviation of the crevasse orientation. The mean absolute deviation provides an estimate of the local degree
156 of dispersion of crevasse orientations. We evaluate the GCD in Section S2 of the supplement by comparing
157 it to two other, previously used crevasse mapping techniques: digital elevation model (DEM) thresholding
158 and manual delineation.

159 We use feature-tracking toolbox GIV to calculate 80-m-resolution glacier-surface-velocity and strain
160 maps for Narsap Sermia, using a frequency-domain multi-pass image correlator (Van Wyk de Vries and
161 Wickert, 2021). We use velocity maps to assess glacier surface strain conditions, and the orientation of
162 crevasses relative to ice flow direction. We also calculate apparent displacements over the surrounding
163 bedrock to correct for georeferencing errors and evaluate local noise levels. We compile three different
164 datasets of image pairs based on the temporal separation between images: short period (1-8 days), medium
165 period (9-90 days), and long period (300 to 430 and 650 to 800 days; 1 or 2 years). This separation allows us
166 to monitor displacements over both regions of rapid ice flow in which surface decorrelation occurs rapidly,
167 and regions of slow ice flow in which long temporal separation is necessary for resolvable displacement to
168 occur. We calculate velocities from a total of 7194 image pairs, of which 330 are short period image pairs,
169 2306 are medium period image pairs, and 4558 are long period image pairs. Calculating a large number
170 of individual velocity maps improves the precision of median velocity maps (Millan and others, 2019; Van
171 Wyk de Vries and Wickert, 2021).

172 We calculate displacements from each Sentinel-2 image pair using iteratively reducing multipass tem-
173 plate matching following the standard GIV workflow (Van Wyk de Vries and Wickert, 2021). We use the
174 standard GIV reference window sizes of 1280 m, 640 m, and 320 m and a 75% window overlap, for a
175 final velocity-map resolution of 80 m. Displacements are evaluated to sub-pixel precision in the final pass
176 through Taylor series expansion of correlation values neighboring the integer extrema. We convert each
177 pair-wise displacement map into a velocity map by dividing it by the temporal separation between images.
178 We then filter each velocity map by removing the value for pixels which have a signal to noise ratio lower
179 than 5 or a peak ratio less than 1.3, exclude values that differ by more than 50% from their immediate

Fig. 3. Diagram the main steps involved in the automated crevasse mapping method. A time series of satellite imagery is convolved with a Gabor filter bank, creating maximum Gabor phase and maximum response angle maps. The maximum Gabor phase map is then thesholded to extract a crevasse network, with the orientation of each crevasse obtained from the maximum response angle map.

180 neighbours (four surrounding cells) and 200% from the mean of their larger local area (25 surrounding
 181 cells), and interpolate across these now-empty pixels using the values of the remaining (i.e. valid) ice-
 182 speed pixels. We do not use a maximum velocity filter so as to capture rapid (>10 km/yr) motion of the
 183 glacier front and frontal melange. These thresholds were manually selected based on local tests to exclude
 184 the majority of pixels with erroneous velocity estimates based on comparison with neighboring pixels and
 185 external datasets. To correct for georeferencing error, we fit a 2-D polynomial surface to the velocities
 186 of non-glacierized (stable) areas in the x and y directions for each image pair, and subtract this to the
 187 velocities across the entire image.

188 We calculate a time series of velocities for each pixel, and average all individual processed velocity
 189 maps into a median velocity map and flow direction map covering the entire 6-year period for each of the
 190 three image temporal separations (short, medium, and long). We compare the velocity time series to time
 191 series of crevasse intensity and orientation, while the median flow direction maps are used to calculate the
 192 angle between crevasses and ice flow direction. We average all individual processed velocity maps into a
 193 median velocity map covering the entire 6-year period. We also calculate annual median velocity maps
 194 for each of the three image temporal separations (short, medium, and long). We calculate longitudinal
 195 (σ_{xx}), transverse (σ_{yy}), and shear (σ_{xy}) strain rate maps from each of the overall and annual median
 196 velocity maps. Finally, we calculate the relative angle between crevasse orientation (calculated using the
 197 GCD described above) and local ice-flow direction, and classify crevasses into three categories: longitudinal
 198 crevasses oriented close to ($0 - 33^\circ$) of the direction of ice flow, transverse crevasses oriented approximately
 199 perpendicular to the direction of ice flow ($66 - 90^\circ$), and crevasses oriented in neither of these directions
 200 ($33 - 66^\circ$).

201 RESULTS

202 We find an overall decrease in crevasse density with distance away from the calving front at Narsap
 203 Sermia, with three main styles of crevassing (Figure 4). The first type of crevasse, oriented approximately
 204 perpendicular to the direction of ice flow, is abundant within 5 km of the glacier marine calving front and
 205 to a lesser degree at subsidiary lacustrine calving fronts. These crevasses form large, arcuate fractures
 206 in the extensively damaged zone proximal to the calving front. The second type of crevasses, oriented
 207 approximately 45° from the direction of ice flow, are most abundant on the flanks of the zone of fast ice
 208 flow at the centre of the valley. The third type, oriented approximately parallel to the direction of ice flow,

Fig. 4. Crevasse orientation map of Narsap Sermia from 17 April 2022, with inset showing the two key crevasse zones: a zone of transverse crevassing near the ice front, and a zone of longitudinal crevassing up-glacier of this. The polar histograms show the angle between the direction of crevassing and direction of ice flow in each inset.

209 are primarily located within the centre of the glacier valley. A 3 km long by 1 km wide region located
210 halfway up the outlet glacier (~ 10 km from the ice front) is dominated by this third, longitudinal crevasse
211 type. While the first, transverse, crevasse type is the most abundant close to the ice front, the second and
212 third crevasse types are also present to a lesser degree.

213 We assess crevasse and velocity changes at three 1 km^2 zones on the glacier representing these main
214 regions: the first “down-glacier” zone is located close to the ice front in the zone of longitudinal crevassing
215 (Figure 5), the second “transitional” zone is located 7.5 km up-glacier at the transition between the
216 longitudinal crevassing and transverse crevassing zones (Figure 6), and the third “up-glacier” zone is
217 located within the zone of transverse crevassing (Figure 7). The down-glacier zone is located in a region
218 of moderate depth, low slope subglacial topography while the transitional zone is on the downstream tip
219 of a subglacial ridge and the up-glacier zone is at the centre of the same subglacial ridge and close to its
220 transition into a subglacial trough (Figure 8e).

221 Crevasses also exhibit seasonal variability, with strong seasonal changes in both the intensity and dom-
222 inant orientation of crevasses in some regions of Narsap Sermia. Crevasse density remains high throughout
223 the year in the down-glacier zone, with close to 100% crevasse coverage throughout the year (Figure 5a).
224 The intensity of secondary (45° and longitudinal) crevassing exhibits minor variability, although transverse
225 crevassing remains dominant at all times. The median angle between crevasse orientation and ice flow in
226 the down-glacier zone varies between 55° and 75° (Figure 5b). Seasonal variability in both crevasse density
227 and orientation is high at the transitional zone, with a summer minimum in degree of crevassing (Figure
228 6a). Crevasse density reaches close to 100% in the winter and spring, but declines to less than 50% in the
229 mid-summer (Figure 6b). The degree of summer (July) crevassing in the transitional zone has increased
230 from 40-50% in 2016 to $\sim 60\%$ in 2021. The median angle between crevasse orientation and ice flow in
231 this zone fluctuates from around 20° in the summer to 70° in late autumn to spring (Figure 6b). In the
232 up-glacier zone the median angle between crevasse orientation and ice flow remains low ($10\text{-}20^\circ$) and the
233 intensity of crevassing remains close to 100% throughout the year (Figures 7a and 7b).

234 Ice velocities show a similar trend in all three of these zones, with a seasonal minima in the late summer
235 and maxima in the early spring (Figures 5c, 6c, 7c). Velocities also show a long-term acceleration, with
236 2021 velocities being around 33% higher than in 2016. In the transitional zone, the yearly velocity maxima
237 coincides with the yearly minima in crevasse density and angle between crevasse orientation and ice flow
238 (Figure 6).

Fig. 5. Time series of crevasse density (b), crevasse orientation relative to direction of ice flow (c), and ice velocity (d) for the 1 km² down-glacier zone at the front of Narsap Sermia (a). The dark line represents the median monthly velocity. Note that the y axes are different to figures 6 and 7 to highlight the seasonal variation in each location.

Fig. 6. Time series of crevasse density (b), crevasse orientation relative to direction of ice flow (c), and ice velocity (d) for the 1 km² transitional zone ~5 km up-glacier from the front of Narsap Sermia (a). The dark line represents the median monthly velocity. Note that the y axes are different to figures 5 and 7 to highlight the seasonal variation in each location.

Fig. 7. Time series of crevasse density (b), crevasse orientation relative to direction of ice flow (c), and ice velocity (d) for the 1 km² up-glacier zone ~10 km up-glacier from the front of Narsap Sermia (a). The dark line represents the median monthly velocity. Note that the y axes are different to figures 5 and 6 to highlight the seasonal variation in each location.

239 The region of high seasonal variation in crevasse orientation is spatially limited to the boundary between
240 the frontal region of transverse crevasses and the up-glacier zone of longitudinal crevasses. This region
241 exhibits a >20 degree variation in median angle between crevasse orientation and ice flow throughout the
242 year (Figure 8c). A broader region exhibits a moderate to high seasonal variation in crevasse density, with
243 the surroundings of the up-glacier zone of longitudinal crevasses all exhibiting a ~20 % seasonal variation
244 in crevasse density (Figure 8d). The up-glacier zone of longitudinal crevassing is located above a subglacial
245 ridge (Figure 8e) and in an area with very low velocity gradients and effective strain rates (Figure 8a and
246 b).

247 DISCUSSION

248 Our automatically processed crevasse orientation maps, based on six years of Sentinel-2 data and 224
249 individual images of Narsap Sermia, provide the first dense time series of changes crevasse change at
250 a major glacier. We first show that the large scale pattern of crevassing remains consistent across the
251 entire study period, with a zone of longitudinal crevassing near the glacier front and a zone of transverse
252 crevassing up-glacier of this. These persistent large-scale crevasse patterns likely relate to the glacier
253 geometry and bed elevation. Conversely, we identify both strong seasonal and multiannual variability
254 when examining time series of crevasse density (the spatial density of crevasses in a given area) and
255 orientation (the median difference between crevasse angle and ice-flow direction). The main glacier trunk
256 exhibits a seasonal minima in degree of crevassing in the late summer, and some regions exhibit a seasonal
257 fluctuation between transverse crevassing (high angle to ice-flow direction) to longitudinal crevassing (low
258 angle to ice-flow direction). Velocity mapping highlights a multiannual increase in ice flow speeds with
259 the greatest increase close to the ice front (Figures 5d, 6d, 7d), which is a possible cause for observed
260 multi-annual increases in crevasse density and changes in crevasse orientation 5-10 km upglacier from the
261 ice front.

262 Our GCD crevasse mapping method can be leveraged to rapidly map the characteristics of thousands
263 of individual crevasses or whole crevasse fields. Using automated instead of manual crevasse mapping
264 methods can enable structural glaciology techniques to be upscaled from single glaciers and time periods
265 to whole ice caps and/or multiple time periods. Our results from Narsap Sermia show that a crevasse
266 map derived from a single time period might not be representative of the glacier's overall conditions. The
267 first implication of this finding is that glacier structure may be more dynamic than previously considered

Fig. 8. Median ice flow speed (a), effective strain rate (b), crevasse orientation seasonality (c), crevasse intensity seasonality (d), and subglacial topography (e). Crevasse orientation and intensity seasonality is calculated as the average of September 2020 to May 2021 minus the average of June 2020 to July 2020. Subglacial topography is obtained from BedMachine v4.0, and is referenced to the local mean sea level (geoid).

268 (Hudleston, 2015; Jennings and Hambrey, 2021), and be a valuable tool for assessing short timescale glacier
269 change. The second implication is methodological: studies aiming to use crevasses to map a glacier's
270 dynamic conditions must account for this temporal variability, as manually mapping crevasses over a single
271 time step may produce a map reflecting transient conditions at this point in time, rather than the longer
272 timescale forcings of interest (e.g., Phillips and others, 2017; Swift and others, 2018; Jones and others,
273 2018; Dell and others, 2019; Jennings and others, 2022).

274 While the GCD described in this study has a number of advantages, it also has certain limitations. An
275 ideal crevasse model would be able to delineate all crevasses in a glacier, regardless of their scale or physical
276 appearance, while also not falsely classifying any other glacier surface features as crevasses. The complex
277 and highly variable nature of a glacier surface makes this a complex task: glaciers can exhibit a wide range
278 of surface expressions (e.g. Herzfeld and others, 2004; Colgan and others, 2016) and features other than
279 crevasses can form linear expressions on a glacier surface, including medial moraines, longitudinal foliation,
280 ogives, and flow banding (Hudleston, 2015; Jones and others, 2018; Jennings and Hambrey, 2021). The GCD
281 is in most cases unable to distinguish between linear expressions on the ice surface related to crevassing and
282 those related to other processes. The GCD can identify sub-pixel resolution crevasses (<10 m in the case of
283 Sentinel-2), but requires them to leave distinct surface expressions, and will likely fail where multiple small
284 crevasses are present within a single pixel. The GCD only identifies a single dominant crevasse orientation
285 at any given pixel, which can result in information loss at pixels where two or more crevasses of different
286 orientations intersect. Finally, the GCD requires a surface expression of crevasses in optical imagery, and
287 will fail to identify crevasses entirely buried by snow (which can be identified using other methods; e.g.
288 Eder and others, 2008; Thompson and others, 2020). Crevasse surface expression and degree of shadowing
289 can also be affected by sun azimuth. We therefore suggest that the GCD be primarily used in areas where
290 (i) crevasses are close to or greater than the resolution of the imagery used to map them, (ii) crevasses
291 are the dominant structural feature on the glacier surface, and (iii) the glacier surface is largely free of
292 snowcover.

293 Our results are not consistent with a binary classification of crevasses into transverse crevasses forming
294 in longitudinal tension, and longitudinal or splaying crevasses forming under longitudinal compression
295 (Glen and Perutz, 1955; Colgan and others, 2016; Jennings and Hambrey, 2021). While we do identify
296 sectors where crevasses are primarily aligned perpendicular or parallel to the direction of ice flow, they
297 retain a wide distribution of orientations (Figure 4). For example in the proximal region to the ice front

298 dominated by longitudinal crevasses, crevasses are found oriented in all directions: while crevasses oriented
299 perpendicular to the direction of ice flow are the most abundant, there are secondary populations oriented
300 $\sim 60^\circ$ and parallel to the direction of ice flow (Figure 4). Crevasses are oriented almost exclusively parallel
301 to the direction of glacier flow in the zone 5-10 km from the calving front, yet the angle between crevasses
302 and the direction of ice flow is commonly as high as $20\text{-}30^\circ$. Our results are in line with prior studies which
303 have highlighted the complex relationship between velocity, strain, and crevasse orientation, particularly
304 in the case of crevasse fields with multiple closely spaced crevasses (Sassolas and others, 1996; Harper and
305 others, 1998; Herzfeld and others, 2004; Colgan and others, 2016). This diversity in crevasse orientation and
306 its potential impact on calving behaviour is largely unaccounted for in the current generation of ice-sheet
307 models.

308 In order for calving to occur, a crevasse must propagate through the entire thickness of the glacier
309 and separate a fragment of the glacier from the main ice mass. Crevasse orientation is, therefore, a first
310 order control on calving as transverse crevasses are more easily able to separate icebergs than longitudinal
311 crevasses. In an endmember case with crevasses oriented parallel to ice flow, fracture opening will simply
312 cause the ice front to splay but be unable to detach any icebergs. This endmember is not realistic as
313 ice-front conditions result in a wider range of crevasse orientations, but some glacier fronts do exhibit a
314 distinctive splaying crevasse pattern (e.g. Glaciar San Quintín, Chile or Svínafellsjökull, Iceland; Swift
315 and others, 2018; Minowa and others, 2021). Crevasse orientation can therefore be both a result of a
316 stable glacier front configuration (for instance with longitudinal compression at a pinning point) and itself
317 a contributor to stability (with a high angle between crevasses and the ice front inhibiting rapid iceberg
318 calving). Many of the current generation of calving models are calibrated using 1D or 2D cross-sectional
319 glacier models (e.g. Benn and others, 2007; Nick and others, 2010; Bassis and Jacobs, 2013; Krug and
320 others, 2014; Lea and others, 2014; Bassis and others, 2021). These models are inherently unable to
321 capture the impact of crevasse orientation on calving rate. Crevasse orientation can be evaluated in 3D
322 discrete element models (Benn and others, 2017; Cook and others, 2018; van Dongen and others, 2020),
323 however these are computationally intensive and cannot easily be coupled to continuum ice-sheet models.
324 Future studies should aim to parameterise for the effect of crevasse orientation on calving rate and iceberg
325 size distributions, so that structural glaciology observations can be used to improve forecasts of future ice
326 mass loss.

327 Finally, we consider the implications of our results for the stability and future evolution of Narsap

328 Sermia. The recent retreat of Narsap Sermia has been well documented in previous studies (Motyka and
329 others, 2017; Davison and others, 2020), and has persisted through our study period. As of early 2022, the
330 front of Narsap Sermia is 1-2 km up-glacier of its 2016 terminus. Can we gain any insight from our crevasse
331 mapping about whether or not Narsap Sermia is likely to retreat into the overdeepened glacial trough?
332 Firstly, we observe a persistent pattern of longitudinal crevasses around 5-10 km up-glacier of the current
333 ice front. This crevasse pattern is diagnostic of compressional longitudinal stresses (Colgan and others,
334 2016; Jennings and Hambrey, 2021), for instance at a pinning point, and conducive to glacier stability.
335 Compressional ice flow as ice exits the overdeepened trough might inhibit rapid ice retreat. Secondly, we
336 observe an up-glacier migration of the frontal zone of transverse crevassing, with a gradual increase in the
337 angle between crevasses and ice-flow direction at the transition between the transverse and longitudinal
338 crevassing zones (Figure 6c). We also observe an increase in ice velocity along the entire central lobe of the
339 glacier, with the largest acceleration occurring close to the ice front. This will be associated with increase
340 longitudinal strain and stress. If longitudinal tension increases sufficiently, it might overcome the present-
341 day compressional flow out of the overdeepened trough, increase ice damage, and promote rapid calving.
342 If this does occur, it will likely be preceded by continued up-glacier migration of the zone of transverse
343 crevassing, and overprinting of the current patch of longitudinal crevasses. Real-time monitoring of the
344 crevasse conditions at Narsap Sermia can enable rapid identification of any dynamic change preceding rapid
345 retreat.

346 CONCLUSIONS

347 We use a novel crevasse detection method to map the crevasse pattern of an entire Greenland outlet glacier,
348 Narsap Sermia, across more than six years of Sentinel-2 data. Our crevasse detection method, based on
349 filtering optical satellite images using a Gabor filter bank, is able to classify both the location and
350 orientation of individual crevasses. We use this to identify both spatial and temporal patterns in crevassing.
351 The 5 km of Narsap Sermia closest to the calving front is dominated by transverse crevassing, while the
352 central region of the outlet glacier is dominated by longitudinal crevassing, approximately parallel to the
353 direction of glacier flow. Both crevasse density and crevasse orientation exhibit strong seasonal variability
354 across much of Narsap Sermia, with a seasonal minima in crevassing in late spring to early summer
355 coincident with a maxima in ice flow speed. Crevassing and velocity also exhibit multiannual changes, with
356 up-glacier propagation of the zone of transverse crevassing coincident with frontal retreat and acceleration.

357 High-resolution, multi-temporal crevasse maps contribute to our understanding of crevasse and calving
358 dynamics, which facilitates forecasting of glacier dynamic change and remains challenging to represent in
359 numerical glacier models.

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